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“We exalt you Mother of the True Light:” Coptic Hymn or Creed, and the Date of Origin

Introduction

Today in the Coptic Church a text precedes the Creed during several services of the Liturgy of the Hours. This text has become known as the “Introduction to the Creed,” [IttC] and is generally recited in the same manner as the Niceno-Constantinopolitan creed that follows it. Text and translation are as such,

ΤΕΝΘΙΣΙ ΜΜΟ ΘΜΑΥ ΜΠΙΟΥΩΙΝΙ	We exalt you, Mother of the true Light. We
ΝΤΑΦΜΥΙ: ΤΕΝΤΩΟΥ ΝΕ Ω ΘΗΘΟΥΛΒ	glorify you, O saint and God-bearer
ΟΥΟΣ ΜΜΑΣΝΟΥΤ: ΧΕ ΛΡΕΜΙΣΙ ΝΑΝ	(<i>Theotokos</i>), for you brought forth unto us
Μ`ΣΩΤΗΡ ΜΠΙΚΟΣΜΟΣ ΤΗΡΦ: ΛΓΙ ΟΥΟΣ	the <i>Savior</i> of the whole <i>world</i> . He came and
ΛΥΩΤ ΗΝΕΝΨΥΧΗ.	saved our <i>souls</i> .

ΟΥΩΟΥ ΝΑΚ ΠΕΝΝΗΒ ΠΕΝΟΥΡΟ	Glory to You, our Master, our King, <i>Christ</i> ,
ΠΙΧΡΙΣΤΟΣ: ΗΨΟΥΨΟΥ ΝΝΙΑΠΟΣΤΟΛΟΣ:	the pride of the <i>Apostles</i> , the crown of the
ΠΙΧΛΟΜ ΗΤΕ ΝΙΜΑΡΤΥΡΟΣ: ΗΘΕΛΗΛ	<i>martyrs</i> , the joy of the <i>righteous</i> , the
ΗΝΙΔΙΚΕΟΣ: ΗΤΑΧΡΟ ΗΝΙΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ: ΗΧΩ	foundation of the <i>churches</i> , the forgiveness of
ΕΒΟΛ ΗΤΕ ΝΙΡΕΧΕΡΙΝΟΒΙ. ¹	sinners.

¹ *Paris BnF Copt.* 11, 22, 34, 69, 75, 76 - ΗΧΩ ΕΒΟΛ ΗΤΕ ΝΙΡΕΧΕΡΙΝΟΒΙ (forgiveness of sinners); *Paris BnF Copt.* 81 – only has ΗΧΩ ΕΒΟΛ (forgiveness). The Arabic is always translated as “غفران الخطايا” (forgiveness of

Abstract: The Coptic “Introduction to the Creed” is a text that precedes the Niceno-Constantinopolitan Creed within the Bohairic Liturgy of the Hours. Because the current rite in the Coptic Orthodox Church includes two components from the Liturgy of the Hours (Matins raising of incense and hourly prayers of the horologion) before the Eucharistic liturgy, the “Introduction to the Creed” is recited twice in such context. However, this text is completely absent from the core of the Eucharistic liturgy or any other liturgical prayers outside the Liturgy of Hours. Traditionally this text is dated to the Council of Ephesus and attributed to Cyril of Alexandria. Although very little scholarship has been done on this text, previous scholarship have challenged its credal status and have proposed that it was composed by some Bohairic Monastic community. The paper at hand will build upon previous scholarship showing that this text is actually a hymn and not intended to be a creed at all. Although the text has strong parallels to Greek texts in the earliest Sahidic Psalmody as well as an Encomium attributed to Cyril of Alexandria, there are significant challenges to dating this text. There is no literary or historical reason to confine its origin to the period of the Council of Ephesus. What we could assert with confidence is that it was present before the 14th century, and likely before the 12th century, based on manuscript evidence.

Keywords: Coptic Introduction to the Creed; Coptic Liturgy of the Hours; Marian Hymn; Copto-Arabic Manuscripts; Cyril of Alexandria; Council of Ephesus.

Resumen: La “Introducción al Credo” en copto es un texto que antecede al Credo Niceno-Constantinopolitano en la Boháirica Liturgia de las Horas. Debido a que el rito actual en la Iglesia Ortodoxa Copta incluye dos componentes de la Liturgia de las Horas (maitines elevando incienso y oraciones por horas del horologion) antes de la liturgia eucarística, la “Introducción al Credo” se recita dos veces en dicho contexto. Sin embargo, este texto está completamente fuera del núcleo de la liturgia eucarística o de cualquier otra oración litúrgica fuera de la Liturgia de las Horas. Tradicionalmente, este texto está fechado en el Concilio de Éfeso y atribuido a Cirilo de Alejandría. Aunque se han realizado muy pocos estudios sobre este texto, estudios anteriores han desafiado su estatus de credo y han propuesto que fue compuesto por alguna comunidad monástica boháirica. Nuestro trabajo se basa en estudios anteriores que muestran que este texto es en realidad un himno y no es en absoluto un credo. Aunque el texto tiene claros paralelismos con los textos griegos de la primera Psalmody sahidica, así como con un Encomio atribuido a Cirilo de Alejandría, existen problemaas importantes para su datación. No hay razón literaria o histórica para limitar su origen al período del Concilio de Éfeso. Lo que podemos afirmar, con certeza, es que estuvo presente antes del siglo XIV y probablemente antes del siglo XII, según la evidencia manuscrita.

Palabras clave: Introducción copta al Credo; Liturgia copta de las Horas; Himno mariano; Manuscritos copto-árabes; Cirilo de Alejandría; Concilio de Éfeso.